

Modeling of lipophilicity of some organic compounds using structural and topological indices

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Abstract : In the present work we have considered miscellaneous set of 48 compounds and modeled their log *P* using classical as well as topological descriptors. The results indicate that the estimation (modeling) of log *P* is very much effective when the structural and topological descriptors are used together. The most appropriate model for the estimation (modeling) of log *P* indicated that by using the combination of structural and topological descriptors the results account for 93% variation in log *P*.

Keywords : Lipophilicity, log *P*, topological descriptors, QSAR.

Introduction

The importance of lipophilicity (log *P*) in Quantitative Structure – Property-Activity-Toxicity Relationships (QSPR/QSAR/QSTR) is well recognized in 1890 when Mayer and Overton noted that the toxicity of organic compounds directly depends upon their lipophilicity expressed as log *P*, where *P* is the partition coefficient of organic compounds between octanol and water. There have been successful efforts to draw up global QSTR models by using log *P* as a single descriptor. Such models are applicable to quite miscellaneous data set¹.

Lipophilicity vis-à-vis hydrophobicity of a molecule is characterized by log *P* which, in turn, is directly related to bio-uptake of chemical by all living beings. Consequently, log *P* mimics almost all the biological behaviour of all organic compounds acting as drugs. It is due to 1 : 1 correlation between log *P* and biological activity. log *P* plays two-fold role, behaving as property as well as activity. This is well demonstrated in our recent review on "The Topology of Molecule and its Lipophilicity"¹.

In the review we have argued that even after the introduction of graph theory and topology in chemistry, very little or no attempts are made to discuss the topology of the molecule and its lipophilicity (log *P*). Also, we have

reviewed the methods of estimation of log *P* using different approaches in all the cases discussed in our review. We have considered log *P* as a quantity (property/activity) and discussed its determination (estimation) using topological indices. Needless to state that topological index is a numerical representation of structure so as to help us in developing 1 : 1 correlation between structure and activity¹.

The present study is the extension of our earlier study discussed in our review¹. Here we have considered miscellaneous set of 48 compounds and modeled their log *P* using classical as well as topological descriptors. The results as discussed below indicate that the estimation (modeling) of log *P* is very much effective when the structural and topological descriptors are used together. The most appropriate model for the estimation (modeling) of log *P* indicated that by using the combination of structural and topological descriptors, the results account for 93% variation in log *P*.

Results and discussion

The set of 48 compounds used along with their adopted log *P* values² are given in Table 1. The structural as well as topological descriptors calculated for these 48 compounds are summarized in Tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 1. Various organic compounds and their log *P* value used in the present study

Compd.	Name of the compound	log <i>P</i>
1	1,2-Propanediol	-0.780
2	Formamide, <i>N,N</i> -dimethyl	-0.930
3	1-Butanol	0.840
4	Propane, 1,2-dichloro	2.250
5	2-Butanol	0.770
6	Ethane, 1,1,2-trichloro	2.010
7	Ethane, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloro	2.190
8	Phenol, 4,4'-(1-methylethylidene)bis	3.640
9	2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, methyl ester	1.280
10	Benzene, 1,2-dichloro	3.280
11	Propane, 1,2,3-trichloro	2.500
12	2-Butanone, oxime	1.690
13	Ethanol, 2-diethylamino	0.050
14	Benzene, 1,4-dichloro	3.280
15	Ethane, 1,2-dichloro	1.830
16	2,4-Pentanediol, 2-methyl	0.580
17	2-Propanol, 1-methoxy	-0.490
18	Benzene, methyl	2.540
19	Phenol, 2,4-dichloro	2.800
20	Ethanol, 2-phenoxy	1.100
21	2,4-Pentanedione	0.050
22	Acetic acid, butyl ester	1.850
23	Hexanedioic-acid	0.230
24	Acetic acid-ethyl ester	0.860
25	1-Butene, 3,4-dichloro	2.600
26	2-Propanol, 1-phenoxy	1.520
27	2-Propenoic acid, 2-methyl-, 2-hydroxyethyl ester	0.300
28	Propane, 2-methoxy-2-methyl	1.430
29	1-Propanol, 2-phenoxy-	1.520
30	Diphenyl ether	4.210
31	Dipentyl ether	4.040
32	Diisopropyl ether	1.520
33	Tetrahydrofuran	0.460
34	Dibutyl ether	3.210
35	Furan	1.340
36	Ethanol	-0.310
37	2,6-Dimethoxytoluene	2.640
38	2,2,2-Trichloroethanol	1.420
39	1,2,4-Trichlorobenzene	4.050
40	1,3-Dichlorobenzene	3.520
41	1,4-Dimethoxybenzene	2.150
42	3-Furanmethanol	0.300
43	3,4-Dichlorotoluene	4.060
44	Acetone	-0.240
45	Acetophenone	1.580
46	Methanol	-0.770
47	Cyclohexanone	0.810
48	Trichloroethene	2.420

The structural descriptors were calculated using ACD Labs software³. While the topological descriptors were calculated by using DRAGON⁴ software, the mutual correlation of structural and topological descriptors⁵ and their correlations with log *P* are demonstrated in Table 3. A perusal of Table 3 shows that none of the descriptors correlated excellently with log *P*. Molecular weight (MW), molar refractivity (MR), index of refraction (IR), polarizability (Pol) and zero-order valence connectivity (${}^0\chi^v$) index, are equally good single parameters correlating with log *P*. The correlation of ${}^0\chi^v$ with log *P* indicates that number of hetero-atoms are very much responsible for the exhibition of log *P* by the set of 48 compounds used by us. We conclude, therefore, that no one-variable model is possible for modeling log *P*. It means that two or more variable models will perhaps be more useful for modeling log *P*. Also, that in multi-parametric models one or more of the above mentioned descriptors (MW, MR, IR, Pol, ${}^0\chi^v$) will be present as one or more of the dominating parameters for modeling log *P*.

In view of the above we have performed multiple linear regression analysis⁶ for modeling log *P*. The variable selection in multiple regression analysis using NCSS software⁶ demonstrated ten statistically significant models (Table 4). However, correlation of number of descriptors with R^2 and R^2_A both (Fig. 1) has shown that we can use up to 7 descriptors for modeling log *P* successfully.

The regression parameters and quality of correlation for the aforementioned models are given in Table 5. A perusal of the Table 5 shows that one-variable model containing MW as a correlating parameter is not statistically significant and the statistically significant models starts from two to more variable models. The data presented in Table 5 also demonstrate that better results are obtained when structural descriptors are used with topological indices. The best 7-parametric model contains four structural descriptors (MW, MV, PC and IR) and three topological indices⁷⁻⁹ (W, Jhetp and PW2). Now, the problem before us is to know whether or not such successive addition of descriptors is justified. That is, we have to investigate that starting from one variable descriptor model for yielding 7-variable model the added parameter has enough contribution to the resulting model. This can be well investigated by the statistical parameter R^2_A (adjusted R^2).

The adjustable- R^2 :

(R^2_A) takes into account of adjustment of R^2 and is given by following expression :

Table 2. Calculated values of topological descriptors for the present set of compounds

Compd.	W	J	Jhetz	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete	Jhetp	$^0\chi$	$^1\chi$	$^2\chi$	$^0\chi^v$	$^1\chi^v$	$^2\chi^v$
1	18	2.540	2.831	2.830	1.834	2.827	1.713	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.179	1.560	1.032
2	18	2.540	3.345	3.344	1.887	3.326	1.694	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.433	1.388	1.069
3	20	2.191	2.290	2.290	1.886	2.289	1.822	4.121	2.414	1.354	3.569	2.023	1.077
4	18	2.540	3.480	3.509	2.540	2.779	2.758	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.552	2.442	1.989
5	18	2.540	2.682	2.682	2.127	2.680	2.044	4.284	2.270	1.802	3.732	1.951	1.257
6	18	2.540	4.267	4.333	2.540	2.920	2.884	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.686	2.519	2.131
7	29	2.993	5.079	5.159	2.993	3.451	3.408	5.155	2.643	2.488	5.690	2.952	2.996
8	516	1.928	2.446	2.446	2.295	2.446	2.267	12.466	7.998	7.735	10.013	5.590	4.719
9	46	3.144	3.761	3.759	2.393	3.754	2.231	5.862	3.181	2.630	4.894	2.260	1.678
10	60	2.279	3.752	3.769	3.135	3.307	3.292	5.983	3.805	3.239	5.577	2.961	2.229
11	31	2.754	3.841	3.875	2.754	3.029	3.004	4.992	2.808	1.922	5.393	3.075	2.140
12	31	2.754	3.518	3.517	2.365	3.510	2.152	4.992	2.808	1.922	4.102	1.984	1.189
13	72	3.074	3.432	3.431	2.305	3.420	2.124	6.406	3.846	2.471	5.723	3.179	1.750
14	62	2.192	3.581	3.596	3.032	3.188	3.175	5.983	3.788	3.365	5.577	2.955	2.309
15	10	1.975	3.083	3.122	1.975	2.234	2.210	3.414	1.914	1.000	3.682	2.104	1.134
16	66	3.389	3.554	3.553	2.895	3.552	2.793	6.784	3.417	4.159	5.679	2.821	2.866
17	32	2.627	3.036	3.034	1.744	3.029	1.606	4.992	2.770	2.183	4.140	1.941	1.304
18	42	2.123	3.021	3.021	3.021	3.021	3.021	5.113	3.394	2.743	4.387	2.411	1.655
19	84	2.346	3.751	3.764	2.909	3.394	2.952	6.853	4.198	3.873	5.947	3.096	2.439
20	133	2.017	2.749	2.748	1.684	2.744	1.562	7.234	4.932	3.646	5.656	3.220	1.885
21	48	2.953	3.427	3.427	2.968	3.425	2.891	5.862	3.126	3.023	4.524	2.115	1.581
22	79	2.716	3.220	3.219	1.927	3.214	1.782	6.406	3.770	2.890	5.438	2.904	1.694
23	151	2.909	3.173	3.173	2.680	3.172	2.599	7.983	4.626	4.072	5.539	3.063	1.995
24	32	2.627	3.446	3.444	1.690	3.435	1.532	4.992	2.770	2.183	4.024	1.904	0.925
25	31	2.754	3.733	3.755	2.965	3.172	3.154	4.992	2.808	1.922	4.837	2.606	1.775
26	174	2.047	2.703	2.702	1.669	2.698	1.549	8.104	5.288	4.475	6.527	3.647	2.473
27	102	3.155	3.776	3.775	2.184	3.768	2.013	7.276	4.181	3.364	5.755	2.957	2.046
28	28	3.168	3.609	3.607	2.183	3.602	2.024	5.207	2.561	2.914	4.908	2.112	2.316
29	168	2.132	2.852	2.851	1.724	2.846	1.596	8.104	5.326	4.253	6.527	3.652	2.424
30	264	1.687	2.427	2.426	1.529	2.423	1.422	8.933	6.449	5.244	7.182	4.230	2.728
31	220	2.691	2.911	2.910	2.093	2.907	1.980	8.364	5.414	3.475	8.065	4.992	3.027
32	48	2.953	3.444	3.442	1.918	3.436	1.760	5.862	3.126	3.023	5.563	2.781	2.234
33	15	2.083	2.321	2.320	1.533	2.317	1.440	3.536	2.500	1.768	3.237	2.077	1.319
34	120	2.595	2.859	2.858	1.923	2.855	1.803	6.950	4.414	2.768	6.651	3.992	2.319
35	15	2.083	2.978	2.977	1.838	2.972	1.712	3.536	2.500	1.768	2.718	1.471	0.793
36	4	1.633	1.868	1.867	1.111	1.864	1.027	2.707	1.414	0.707	2.154	1.023	0.316
37	150	2.446	3.438	3.437	2.258	3.433	2.113	8.268	5.291	4.127	7.049	3.469	2.288
38	28	3.168	5.126	5.191	2.760	3.718	2.927	5.207	2.561	2.914	5.056	2.371	3.289
39	84	2.346	3.936	3.958	3.172	3.381	3.363	6.853	4.198	3.873	6.634	3.439	2.809
40	61	2.231	3.656	3.671	3.078	3.240	3.226	5.983	3.788	3.377	5.577	2.955	2.313
41	125	2.174	3.130	3.129	1.999	3.125	1.863	7.397	4.864	3.703	6.126	3.046	1.880
42	43	2.140	2.799	2.798	1.937	2.795	1.825	5.113	3.432	2.559	3.795	2.052	1.290
43	84	2.346	3.652	3.665	3.172	3.310	3.298	6.853	4.198	3.873	6.500	3.372	2.732
44	9	2.324	2.963	2.962	2.342	2.960	2.249	3.577	1.732	1.732	2.908	1.204	0.908
45	88	2.228	3.018	3.018	2.854	3.017	2.824	6.690	4.305	3.642	5.295	2.865	1.922
46	1	1.000	1.333	1.332	0.512	1.327	0.455	2.000	1.000	0.000	1.447	0.447	0.000
47	307	1.818	1.861	1.861	1.819	1.861	1.812	9.803	6.877	5.655	9.134	6.414	5.072
48	18	2.540	6.215	6.352	3.143	3.740	3.683	4.284	2.270	1.802	4.479	2.077	1.625

Table 3. Calculated values of structural parameters for the compounds used in the present study

Compd.	MW	MR	MV	PC	IR	ST	D	Pol
1	76.094	18.970	73.400	182.300	1.430	38.000	1.036	7.520
2	73.094	19.850	82.600	186.000	1.396	25.700	0.884	7.870
3	74.122	22.110	92.000	208.000	1.395	26.000	0.805	8.760
4	112.986	25.600	101.200	225.700	1.419	24.700	1.116	10.150
5	74.122	22.070	92.400	205.400	1.393	24.300	0.801	8.750
6	133.404	25.820	96.000	224.400	1.450	29.700	1.388	10.230
7	167.849	30.620	107.800	260.200	1.479	33.900	1.556	12.140
8	228.286	68.160	199.500	519.700	1.598	46.000	1.143	27.020
9	102.132	26.940	114.900	253.100	1.385	23.500	0.888	10.680
10	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280
11	147.431	30.450	112.500	264.200	1.453	30.300	1.309	12.070
12	87.120	24.510	96.500	219.100	1.421	26.500	0.900	9.710
13	117.189	35.100	132.300	313.200	1.443	31.400	0.885	13.910
14	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280
15	98.959	21.010	84.300	188.600	1.412	25.000	1.173	8.330
16	118.174	32.840	123.000	296.800	1.446	33.800	0.960	13.010
17	90.121	23.810	98.800	225.000	1.397	26.900	0.912	9.440
18	92.138	31.070	105.700	244.900	1.499	28.800	0.871	12.320
19	163.001	37.920	111.700	294.000	1.593	47.800	1.458	15.030
20	138.164	39.090	127.400	320.400	1.525	39.900	1.084	15.500
21	100.116	25.270	105.300	241.200	1.395	27.500	0.950	10.010
22	116.158	31.620	131.000	295.500	1.397	25.800	0.886	12.530
23	146.141	32.970	116.800	314.400	1.476	52.400	1.250	13.070
24	88.105	22.350	98.000	216.000	1.373	23.500	0.898	8.860
25	124.996	29.960	112.800	254.500	1.443	25.900	1.108	11.870
26	152.190	43.690	144.300	357.600	1.517	37.600	1.054	17.320
27	132.158	33.110	128.900	309.700	1.427	33.200	1.024	13.120
28	88.148	26.920	117.400	245.800	1.375	19.100	0.750	10.670
29	152.190	43.690	144.300	357.600	1.517	37.600	1.054	17.320
30	170.207	52.690	160.000	398.300	1.572	38.400	1.063	20.890
31	158.281	50.120	199.900	449.600	1.415	25.500	0.791	19.870
32	102.175	31.500	134.600	285.200	1.384	20.100	0.758	12.490
33	72.106	20.050	79.700	184.700	1.416	28.800	0.904	7.940
34	130.228	40.850	166.900	370.000	1.404	24.100	0.780	16.190
35	68.074	18.550	72.200	161.200	1.427	24.800	0.942	7.350
36	46.068	12.840	59.000	128.400	1.354	22.300	0.780	5.090
37	152.190	44.430	153.700	358.200	1.489	29.500	0.990	17.610
38	149.404	27.360	93.200	238.800	1.498	43.000	1.602	10.840
39	181.447	40.930	125.200	314.800	1.567	39.900	1.448	16.220
40	147.002	36.040	113.300	279.000	1.548	36.700	1.297	14.280
41	138.164	39.600	137.400	320.600	1.488	29.600	1.005	15.700
42	98.100	25.000	86.000	214.700	1.492	38.800	1.140	9.910
43	161.029	40.860	129.600	316.600	1.543	35.600	1.242	16.200
44	58.079	15.970	75.100	156.500	1.345	18.800	0.772	6.330
45	120.149	36.280	120.900	292.400	1.511	34.100	0.993	14.380
46	32.042	8.210	42.500	88.600	1.310	18.800	0.753	3.250
47	194.313	57.910	200.200	492.800	1.490	36.700	0.970	22.950
48	131.388	25.760	89.100	210.400	1.489	31.000	1.474	10.210

Table 4. Correlation matrix showing correlation among various parameters

	log P	W	J	Jhetz	Jhetm	Jhetv	Jhete	Jhetp	PW2	PW3	$^0\chi$	$^1\chi$		
log P	1													
W	0.389	1												
J	-0.067	-0.233	1											
Jhetz	0.297	-0.291	0.628	1										
Jhetm	0.298	-0.291	0.617	1.000	1									
Jhetv	0.492	-0.080	0.481	0.717	0.713	1								
Jhete	0.185	-0.208	0.818	0.798	0.786	0.657	1							
Jhetp	0.518	-0.111	0.402	0.753	0.753	0.980	0.572	1						
PW2	0.381	0.263	0.523	0.489	0.480	0.637	0.652	0.560	1					
PW3	0.556	0.455	0.127	0.217	0.211	0.416	0.355	0.362	0.648	1				
$^0\chi$	0.459	0.916	0.037	-0.079	-0.085	0.149	0.112	0.079	0.501	0.642	1			
$^1\chi$	0.485	0.928	-0.139	-0.191	-0.195	0.061	-0.022	0.002	0.433	0.672	0.975	1		
$^2\chi$	0.463	0.882	-0.003	-0.048	-0.053	0.224	0.126	0.157	0.590	0.630	0.961	0.938		
$^3\chi$	0.537	0.880	-0.247	-0.150	-0.152	0.126	-0.041	0.086	0.442	0.762	0.903	0.948		
$^0\chi^v$	0.622	0.848	0.098	0.078	0.075	0.277	0.150	0.242	0.534	0.667	0.943	0.913		
$^1\chi^v$	0.578	0.855	-0.020	-0.060	-0.061	0.176	-0.030	0.157	0.444	0.632	0.901	0.909		
$^2\chi^v$	0.543	0.742	0.143	0.173	0.173	0.363	0.129	0.358	0.577	0.565	0.808	0.761		
$^3\chi^v$	0.581	0.777	-0.149	-0.035	-0.033	0.262	-0.108	0.274	0.394	0.671	0.780	0.808		
MW	0.692	0.728	0.064	0.288	0.288	0.448	0.201	0.459	0.564	0.696	0.833	0.807		
MR	0.636	0.894	-0.062	-0.039	-0.042	0.211	0.045	0.175	0.492	0.691	0.957	0.962		
MV	0.544	0.841	0.095	-0.074	-0.079	0.115	0.079	0.061	0.439	0.589	0.919	0.903		
PC	0.546	0.891	0.042	-0.064	-0.068	0.156	0.061	0.107	0.472	0.638	0.965	0.953		
IR	0.646	0.528	-0.180	0.229	0.229	0.490	0.159	0.492	0.562	0.734	0.631	0.670		
ST	0.268	0.494	-0.044	0.152	0.152	0.353	0.113	0.342	0.459	0.538	0.588	0.582		
D	0.436	0.029	0.093	0.664	0.670	0.617	0.308	0.707	0.393	0.374	0.131	0.102		
Pol	0.636	0.894	-0.062	-0.039	-0.042	0.211	0.045	0.175	0.492	0.691	0.957	0.962		
	$^2\chi$	$^3\chi$	$^0\chi^v$	$^1\chi^v$	$^2\chi^v$	$^3\chi^v$	MW	MR	MV	PC	IR	ST	D	Pol
$^2\chi$	1													
$^3\chi$	0.908	1												
$^0\chi^v$	0.898	0.860	1											
$^1\chi^v$	0.844	0.846	0.967	1										
$^2\chi^v$	0.837	0.752	0.912	0.894	1									
$^3\chi^v$	0.764	0.854	0.878	0.922	0.870	1								
MW	0.826	0.815	0.919	0.875	0.892	0.863	1							
MR	0.924	0.926	0.977	0.960	0.864	0.879	0.896	1						
MV	0.832	0.796	0.958	0.953	0.818	0.804	0.783	0.942	1					
PC	0.900	0.867	0.982	0.975	0.860	0.851	0.856	0.980	0.982	1				
IR	0.716	0.773	0.642	0.599	0.628	0.656	0.808	0.713	0.459	0.587	1			
ST	0.649	0.615	0.512	0.491	0.545	0.505	0.697	0.552	0.326	0.491	0.833	1		
D	0.212	0.225	0.251	0.194	0.393	0.327	0.603	0.215	-0.005	0.119	0.678	0.672	1	
Pol	0.924	0.926	0.977	0.960	0.864	0.879	0.896	1.000	0.942	0.980	0.713	0.551	0.215	1

$$R^2_A = 1 - (1 - R^2) (n - 1/n - k - 1)$$

If a variable is added that does not contribute its fair share, then R^2_A will actually decline. This parameter R^2_A

is particularly important when the number of independent variables is larger relative to the sample size. R^2 may appear artificially high if the number of variables is high

Fig. 1. Correlation of R^2 and R^2_A with number of descriptors used.

Table 5. Cross validation parameters for the proposed models

Model (eq.)	Parameters used	N	PRESS/ SSY	R^2_{CV}	SPRESS	PSE
1	MW	48	1.0871	-0.0871	1.0239	1.0023
2	IR, ST	48	0.5275	0.4725	0.8429	0.8161
3	MW, IR, ST	48	0.3147	0.6853	0.7097	0.6795
4	MW, IR, ST, $^3\chi$	48	0.2654	0.7346	0.6720	0.6360
5	MW, IR, ST, $^3\chi$, Jhetm	48	0.2466	0.7534	0.6603	0.6177
6	MW, IR, ST, $^3\chi$, Jhetm, $^2\chi^v$	48	0.2314	0.7686	0.6527	0.6032
7	MW, IR, W, PC, MV, PW2, Jhetv	48	0.1508	0.8492	0.5507	0.5027

compared to the sample size. In fact, R^2 will always increase when an independent variable is added, while R^2_A will decrease if the added variable does not reduce the unexplained variation enough to affect the loss of degrees of freedom.

The use of seven parameters for modeling log P is also in accordance to the rule of thumb^{10,11}.

Optimum number of descriptors to be used : Rule of thumb :

Linear multiple regression⁶ is the technique that has been most used in quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR), which employs the least-squares method to find out the equation of "best-fit" of biological captivity with a given combination of correlating parameters. The limitation and some common pitfall of multiple regression analysis were pointed out by Tute^{10,11}. Accordingly, there must be a sufficient number of compounds included in the analysis to enable statistical significance to be reached, despite inevitable error in measurement. A rule of thumb was involved^{10,11} that at least five data point (compounds) should be included for every parameters and they themselves should be well "spread" and one must avoid the

particular danger of including one extreme value of any parameter, as a "best-line" will inevitably pass through the extreme points. Looking to these requirements we observed that all the 14 models proposed by us full fills the requirement of rule of thumb^{10,11}.

However, this rule of thumb doesn't decide the optimum number of descriptors to be used in the proposed model. This, however, we can do by plotting a graph between the number of parameters used in the models against corresponding values of R^2 and R^2_A . Such a correlation as shown in Fig. 1 indicates that the optimum number of descriptors to be used is 6 to 7.

We now discuss in detail the proposed models as recorded in Table 5. Before that it is worthy to mention that the data presented in Table 5 indicate that R^2 goes on increasing with each addition descriptors, while Se goes on decreasing with successive addition of descriptors. It means that both statistics as well as quality of the model goes on increasing. As we go from one variable model to seven variable models. Also that no topological index has any favorable contribution up to three (3) variable models. In all the proposed models structural parameters

MW, IR and ST are present as the correlating parameters. The connectivity and extended connectivity based indices alone combine with these three structural parameters improving statistics as well as the quality of the models.

A perusal of Table 5 indicates that out of the descriptors used only MW is the better parameter to model $\log P$. The models based on MW is found as below :

$$\log P = -1.2947 + 0.0240 (\pm 0.0037)MW \quad (1)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.6366, R^2 = 0.4791, R^2_A = 0.4678,$$

$$F = 42.313, Q = 1.0872$$

This eq. (1) shows that though MW is the only best parameter for correlating with $\log P$, the resulting model is not that statistically significant.

A stepwise regression yielded two-variable model containing IR and ST as the correlating parameters. However, the model does not contain MW as the one of the correlating parameters. However, all other higher parametric models invariably contained MW as one of the correlating parameters. The obtained two-variable model containing IR, ST, as the correlating parameters is found as below :

$$\log P = -34.0940 + 27.9136 (\pm 3.2024)IR -$$

$$0.1587 (\pm 0.0285)ST \quad (2)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.5241, R^2 = 0.6547, R^2_A = 0.6393,$$

$$F = 42.657, Q = 1.5438$$

In our earlier communication¹ we have established ST as the inverse steric factor which means that electronic and steric effects influence the exhibition of $\log P$ for the set of compounds used in the present study.

Successive addition of MW to the above eq. (2) results into considerable improvement in the statistics as well as quality of the model. The resulting three-variable model is found as below :

$$\log P = -24.0215 + 19.5632 (\pm 3.2942)IR -$$

$$0.1664 (\pm 0.0247)ST + 0.0192 (\pm 0.0044)MW \quad (3)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.4413, R^2 = 0.7606, R^2_A = 0.7443,$$

$$F = 46.600, Q = 1.9762$$

We observe that in eq. (3) the coefficient of MW is small and positive. It means that the steric factor and the electronic factors are more dominating for the exhibition of $\log P$. It is worthy to mention that in all the higher parametric models MW is invariably present as one of the correlating parameters. Same is the case with the parameter ST. In seven-parametric model ST is contained in PC (Parachor).

Now, in the four-parametric model onward one or more topological indices are present resulting into im-

proved statistics and quality of the model. Addition of topological descriptor ${}^3\chi$ improves the quality of the model expressed in eq. (3). This four-parametric model is found as below :

$$\log P = -27.9333 + 22.3456 (\pm 3.3174)IR -$$

$$0.1741 (\pm 0.0230)ST + 0.0254 (\pm 0.0098)MW -$$

$$0.3601 (\pm 0.1461){}^3\chi \quad (4)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.4178, R^2 = 0.7903, R^2_A = 0.7707,$$

$$F = 40.502, Q = 2.1276$$

The added parameter ${}^3\chi$ has negative coefficient in eq. (4) meaning there by that decrease in the third-order connectivity is favorable for the exhibition of $\log P$ for the set of compounds used.

Further addition of Balaban type index (Jhetm) yields still better model. However, the improvement of statistics is not that big as compared to the addition of ${}^3\chi$ to eq. (3). This five-parametric model is found as below :

$$\log P = -30.5085 + 24.7919 (\pm 3.6032)IR -$$

$$0.1846 (\pm 0.0235)ST + 0.0319 (\pm 0.0062)MW -$$

$$0.6267 (\pm 0.2206){}^3\chi - 0.2904 (\pm 0.1824)Jhetm \quad (5)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.4106, R^2 = 0.8022, R^2_A = 0.7786,$$

$$F = 34.065, Q = 2.1812$$

The added Jhetm has negative coefficient indicating that decrease in extended connectivity is favorable for the exhibition of $\log P$.

Successive addition of ${}^2\chi^v$ improves the quality of the model as shown below :

$$\log P = -28.6936 + 23.2995 (\pm 3.7155)IR -$$

$$0.1846 (\pm 0.0233)ST + 0.0402 (\pm 0.0086)MW -$$

$$0.5882 (\pm 0.2197){}^3\chi - 0.3021 (\pm 0.1805)Jhetm -$$

$$0.3462 (\pm 0.2455){}^2\chi^v \quad (6)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.4058, R^2 = 0.8113, R^2_A = 0.7837,$$

$$F = 29.386, Q = 2.2196$$

Once again the added parameter ${}^2\chi^v$ has negative coefficient. This indicates that decrease in second-order valance connectivity as well as decrease in the number of hetero-atoms is favorable for the exhibition of $\log P$.

Finally, a seven-variable model as given below is found to be most appropriate for the exhibition of $\log P$.

$$\log P = -31.5327 + 22.7046 (\pm 2.8170)IR -$$

$$0.1036 (\pm 0.0124)PC + 0.0243 (\pm 0.0066)MW +$$

$$0.2250 (\pm 0.0240)MV + 0.5091 (\pm 0.2302)Jhetv -$$

$$4.4582 (\pm 1.3728)PW2 +$$

$$0.00074 (\pm 0.0027)W \quad (7)$$

$$N = 48, Se = 0.3424, R^2 = 0.8690, R_A^2 = 0.8450, \\ F = 37.898, Q = 2.7225$$

The eq. (7) indicates that steric and topological parameters greatly influence the exhibition of $\log P$. The coefficient of W is positive but its magnitude is very small. This shows that steric parameter is favorable for the exhibition of $\log P$. Furthermore, the positive sign of MV indicates that increase in molar volume is favorable for exhibition of $\log P$.

On the basis of Pogliani's quality factor^{12,13} Q , which is the ratio of R/Se , we found that the highest value belongs to eq. (7) meaning, thereby, that model 7 is the most appropriate model for modeling the $\log P$ activity of present set of compounds.

We have also calculated the cross validated parameters for all the seven models and are reported in Table 5. The SPRESS as well as PSE are good parameters to be used for discussing the uncertainty in prediction. The lower the value of these parameters, the better will be the predictive ability of the model. A perusal of Table 5 shows that both these parameters go on decreasing as we pass from one- to eight-variable models and that it is the lowest for the model 8. Hence, once again, we find that the most appropriate model for modeling $\log P$.

It is argued that PRESS is a good estimate of the real predictive error of the model. If PRESS is smaller than SSY, the model predicts better than chance and can be considered statistically significant. The ratio PRESS/SSY can be used to calculate approximate confidence intervals of prediction of new observations (compounds). To be a reasonable QSAR model, PRESS/SSY should be smaller than 0.4 and the value of this ratio smaller than 0.1 indicates an excellent model. A perusal of Table 5 shows that except for the three-parametric model, all other higher parametric models have PRESS/SSY < 0.4 thereby indicating them to be reasonable models. This ratio for the eight-parametric model is more or less nearer 0.1 indicating it to have the best prediction capacity. The highest R_{CV}^2 value for model 7 confirms our findings.

Now the problem before us is to make a choice for better model for modeling $\log P$. The most favorable choice is to decide among eqs. (5) and (6). This can be done by estimating $\log P$ from each of these equations and compare the estimated values of $\log P$ with the observed values of $\log P$. The equation which yields estimated $\log P$ closer to observed [experimental] $\log P$ will be the most appropriate model for modeling $\log P$. This can be better judged by calculating residual i.e. difference between observed and calculated $\log P$ values. The

Table 6. Values of observed and estimated $\log P$ using model 7

Compd.	Actual $\log P$	Predicted $\log P$	Residual
1	-0.780	-0.830	0.050
2	-0.930	0.039	-0.969
3	0.840	0.266	0.574
4	2.250	1.934	0.316
5	0.770	0.313	0.457
6	2.010	2.098	-0.088
7	2.190	2.578	-0.388
8	3.640	3.648	-0.008
9	1.280	1.096	0.184
10	3.280	3.279	0.001
11	2.50	2.327	0.173
12	1.690	1.012	0.678
13	0.050	0.904	-0.854
14	3.280	3.241	0.039
15	1.830	1.575	0.255
16	0.580	0.408	0.172
17	-0.490	0.173	-0.663
18	2.540	2.596	-0.056
19	2.800	2.757	0.043
20	1.100	1.468	-0.368
21	0.050	0.695	-0.645
22	1.850	1.191	0.659
23	0.230	-0.856	0.911
24	0.860	0.304	0.556
25	2.600	2.736	-0.136
26	1.520	1.732	-0.212
27	0.300	0.461	-0.161
28	1.430	1.453	-0.023
29	1.520	1.738	-0.218
30	4.210	3.329	0.881
31	4.040	3.429	0.611
32	1.520	1.995	-0.475
33	0.460	-0.175	0.635
34	3.210	2.525	0.685
35	1.340	0.880	0.460
36	-0.310	-0.590	0.280
37	2.640	3.232	-0.592
38	1.420	1.305	0.115
39	4.050	3.631	0.419
40	3.520	3.275	0.245
41	2.150	2.838	-0.688
42	0.300	0.774	-0.474
43	4.060	3.394	0.666
44	-0.240	0.127	-0.367
45	1.580	2.222	-0.642
46	-0.770	-0.361	-0.409
47	0.810	1.719	-0.909
48	2.420	3.139	-0.719

Fig. 2. Correlation showing observed and estimated log *P* using model 7.

model (eq. (7)) with least residuals is the best model. For arriving at the final conclusion we have plotted a graph between observed and estimated log *P* using model 7 (Table 6). Such a graph as shown in Fig. 2 indicates that the model expressed by eq. (7) is the most appropriate model for modeling log *P*.

Conclusions :

On the basis of above, we may conclude that :

- (i) Topological parameters along with physico-chemical parameters are capable of modeling lipophilicity of the present set of compounds.
- (ii) Branching is not favoured for exhibition of log *P*.
- (iii) Increase in molar volume is favorable for exhibition of log *P*.
- (iv) Decrease in the number of hetero-atoms is favorable for the exhibition of log *P*.

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